

1 **Improving Productivity while managing extensive Molecular Dynamics simulation data**

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9 Abstract

10 **Background.** This paper discusses the difficulties experienced by bioinformaticians while
11 working with extensive data generated from extended molecular dynamics simulations. For
12 better experimental analysis, it often becomes crucial to conduct simulations up to extended
13 periods of time. When with limited resources, running a complete simulation up to a desired
14 length of time can become quite difficult to be performed at one go. So, a new approach is
15 proposed to simplify handling such data for better productivity.

16
17 **Methods.** Development of a front-end interface.

18 **Results.** Showing improvements in usability.

19 **Discussion.** Comparing a command line vs graphical interface approach for managing extended
20 molecular dynamics simulations reveal the benefits of the latter by proposed method of use.

21 Introduction

22 Molecular dynamics (Marco De Vivo 2016) simulations have become a great deciding factor in
23 drug development in today's time. One such molecular dynamics software for the same is
24 Desmond (Kevin J. Bowers 2006). For better experimental analysis, it often becomes crucial to
25 conduct simulations up to extended periods of time. When with limited resources, running a
26 complete simulation up to a desired length of time can become quite difficult to be performed at
27 one go. The solution to this is to break them up into smaller time intervals and conduct them
28 separately but sequentially. Such simulations can often take many days to complete. Each of
29 these sequential simulations, starting from the end of the first simulation, becomes an extended
30 simulation with the help of checkpoints, which contain information about simulation progress. At
31 the end of the complete full-length simulation, bioinformaticians have to consolidate all of these
32 generated data that gets accumulated. If there are n number of extended simulations, there would
33 be $n+1$ number of trajectories (Robert T. McGibbon 2015) generated, which contain
34 conformational information of the 3D protein structure that had undergone simulation. In order
35 to view the complete trajectory of the structure starting from 0 unit time until the end of the
36 simulation, it would be essential to combine all of these sequential trajectories into one single
37 and complete trajectory. Only then would it be possible to observe and interpret the
38 corresponding plots pertaining to molecular statistics of the corresponding simulation.
39 Combining all these trajectories is only possible with the help of commands. This can become
40 difficult to manage when a huge number of sequential simulations have been performed. To
41 make this process easier for bioinformaticians, a new approach is proposed.

42 Materials & Methods

43 By using *Tkinter*, one of Python's own graphical user interface (GUI) libraries, a front-end
44 interface has been developed to make it a lot more convenient for the user to merge trajectories.
45 The mini-tool named *TrajectoryMergeAssist*, archived and documented on Zenodo (Avimanyu
46 B. 2018), allows the user to easily choose the required files on the GUI and merge them with the
47 help of the command that would quietly run for the user on the back-end. The software is
48 available on GitHub and is Open Source under GPL 3.0.

49 **System configuration used:**50 **Own System:**

51 Operating System: Ubuntu Linux 16.04 LTS 64 bit

52 GPU: Asus NVIDIA Maxwell Titan X 12 GB

53 CPU: Intel i7 4770K at 3.5 Ghz

54 256 GB SSD

55 500 GB + 2 TB HDD

56 32 GB DDR3 RAM

57 **Lab System:**

58 Operating System: Ubuntu Linux 14.04 LTS 64 bit

59 GPU: Zotac NVIDIA Kepler GT730 2 GB

60 CPU: Intel i3 2100 at 3.1 Ghz

61 500 GB HDD

62 8 GB DDR3 RAM

63 The following screenshot shows a simulation being extended for a prolonged molecular
 64 dynamics simulation for a protein structure with PDB id 5KW2 built in a TIP3P solvent model
 65 on Desmond (D. E. Shaw Research, n.d.) running via Maestro (Schrödinger, n.d.):

66 Example of extending a simulation up to 2.4 ns that has already run until 1.2 ns on Desmond
 67 with a checkpoint (“cpt”) file:

The screenshot displays the Maestro software interface. The central window shows the 'Model System' configuration for a Desmond simulation. The 'Simulation' section is set to 'total' 2.4 ns, with a 'Recording interval (ps)' of 1.0 for 'trajectory' and 1.0 for 'energy'. The 'Ensemble class' is 'NPT', and the 'Temperature (K)' is 300.0 and 'Pressure (bar)' is 1.01325. A 'Desmond' job window is open, showing the job name '5KW2_TIP3P_Extended_System_MD_8-5-18' and a 'Run' button. A 'Job Log' window is also open, displaying a list of jobs and their status, along with a 'Multisim summary' for 'Tue May 8 13:46:41 2018'. The summary indicates that Stage 8 was completed successfully, Stage 5 was skipped, and the total duration was 0h 18' 53".

Job ID	Name	Status	Start
iborg-desktop-0-5af154db	preparcard-protasn	completed	finished
iborg-desktop-0-5af154db	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-incorporated	finished	2018-0
iborg-desktop-0-5af15874	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-incorporated	finished	2018-0
iborg-desktop-0-5af15879	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-completed	finished	2018-0
iborg-desktop-0-5af1591a	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-completed	finished	2018-0
iborg-desktop-0-5af1594a	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-completed	finished	2018-0
iborg-desktop-0-5af15978	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-completed	finished	2018-0
iborg-desktop-0-5af159ab	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-completed	finished	2018-0
iborg-desktop-0-5af159db	SKW2_TIP3P_System_MD_8-completed	finished	2018-0

```

Multisim summary (Tue May 8 13:46:41 2018):
Stage 1 completed.
Stage 2 completed.
Stage 3 completed.
Stage 4 completed.
Stage 5 was skipped.
Stage 6 completed.
Stage 7 completed.
Stage 8 completed.
Total duration: 0h 18' 53"
Total GPU time: 0h 18' 7" (used by 7 subjob(s))
Multisim completed.
  
```

68

69 Discussion

70 *Current method of merging trajectories:*

71 Commands:

72 Version 18-1 or later

73 `$SCHRODINGER/run trj_merge.py out.cms traj1 traj2 -o merged`

74 Earlier versions

75 `$SCHRODINGER/run -FROM desmond manipulate_trj.py input.cms outfile in-trj1 in-trj2`

76 Even with a powerful Nvidia Titan X GPU, it approximately takes 20 minutes for a simulation of
77 1.2 ns to complete. For optimum analysis and interpretations, simulation times can be extended
78 up to 100 ns or even 1000 ns for absolute confirmations of inferences. When it comes to a huge
79 number of extended simulations for such experiments, using commands for merging n number of
80 extended trajectories with the initial one can eventually become quite inconvenient.

81 *Proposed method of merging trajectories:*

82 A user-friendly graphical user interface (GUI):

83 The number of trajectories to choose has been set as two in the GUI, assuming that further
84 extended simulations would be decided based on observing and interpreting the first combined
85 outcome as a statistical plot. Future merging can be done with merged files already made via this
86 tool. It also takes care of merging trajectories irrespective of the version of Desmond installed
87 and also generates an “-out.cms” file instead of “.cms” for version 2018-1 or later which happens
88 during command line usage.

89

90 Selecting the existing “-out.cms” file obtained from previous simulations:

91

92 Confirming selection 1:

93

94 Choosing first trajectory:

95 Confirmation 2:

96

6

97 Choosing second trajectory:

98

99 Final confirmation for second trajectory selection:

100

7

101 Beginning merge:

102 **Results**

103 New merged trajectory “_trj” and “-out.cms” file will be created in the same directory. The time
104 taken for completing this procedure depends on the size of the input files (original and extended
105 simulation times):

106

107 Viewing the statistical plots from 0-2.4 ns with the newly obtained trajectory:

108

109

110

111 Conclusions

112 The user need not worry about the corresponding command for merging trajectories as it is taken
113 care of with the help of a simple click on the GUI. This improves usability by a huge extent and
114 makes it very convenient for the user to manage multiple extended trajectories. Additional
115 features such as independent execution regardless of Desmond version and making the output
116 file ready for viewing on Maestro after merging, makes it even more convenient.

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10

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